

Navigating stakeholder dynamics and policy challenges in the Circular Economy: A focus on bio-based soil improvers and fertilising products

Magdalena Andrunik^{a*}, Marzena Smol^a

^aMineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences, Wybickiego 7a Str.,31-261 Cracow, Poland, andrunik@meeri.pl, smol@meeri.pl

*Corresponding author: Magdalena Andrunik, Mineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences, Wybickiego 7a Str.,31-261 Cracow, Poland, phone: (48) 12 617-16-53, andrunik@meeri.pl

"Analysis of Stakeholders in the Soil Improvers Sector"

Dear Respondent,

This questionnaire is dedicated to identifying key stakeholders in the **EU soil improvers sector** in the context of a circular bioeconomy approach to the waste hierarchy, and the creation of sustainable soil improvers in support of soil health in Europe.

Soil improvers are defined as a material added to soil in situ, whose main function is to maintain or improve its physical and/or chemical and/or biological properties (except for liming materials). A tailored soil improver is a material obtained from a food processing residue stream which has been identified and tested for adding to soil. This also includes organic fertilisers. Applying circular bioeconomy methods to the food industry value chain, improving the use of residue streams and regional production of soil improvers will enhance food system sustainability and so reduce waste.

A **stakeholder** is a person, group, or organization with a vested interest, or stake, in the decision-making and activities of a project and is interested in the project's outcome or execution. Stakeholders are typically the members of a project team, project managers, executives, project sponsors, customers, and the end-users. Stakeholders are people who will be affected by your project at any point in its life cycle, and their input can directly or indirectly impact the outcome. Stakeholders can have a direct or indirect influence on the activities or projects of an organization. Their support is often required for project success.

The questionnaire is a part of the international project *Delivering Soil improvers through improved recycling and processing solutions for food industry residues streams* (**DeliSoil**), funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant Agreement No. 101112855 (DeliSoil).

There are no personal data collected.

I PART. Stakeholders' importance and influence analysis

Q1. Using a scale from 0 to 4, where 0 represents "not at all important" and 4 represents "very important," please assess the importance/significance of the following stakeholders for the soil improvers sector. (give '+')

Stakeholder group	Not at all important (0)	Low importance (1)	Neutral (2)	Important (3)	Very Important (4)	No opinion
Consumers						
Civil society						
Local society						
Non-profit organizations (NGOs)						
Farmers						
Agricultural associations						
Media						
Food and beverage producers						
Fertiliser producers						
Soil amendments producers						
Waste management facilities						
Scientists						
Education sector						
Research and development sector						
Financial investment institutions						
Research funding agencies						
Policy makers (international level)						
Policy makers (national level)						
Policy makers (regional level)						
Industry regulators (wastewater quality, noise, sludge quality)						
Health and safety inspectors & Controlling institutions						
Government officials						
National Sectoral networks						
Regional Sectoral networks						
International Sectoral networks						
Other.....						

Q2. Using a scale from 0 to 4, where 0 represents "no influence" and 4 represents "very high influence," please evaluate the influence/actual interest of the following stakeholders for the soil improvers sector. (give '+')

Stakeholder	No influence (0)	Low influence (1)	Neutral (2)	High influence (3)	Very high influence (4)	No opinion
Consumers						
Civil society						
Local society						
Non-profit organizations (NGOs)						
Farmers						
Agricultural associations						
Media						
Food and beverage producers						
Fertiliser producers						
Soil amendments producers						
Waste management facilities						
Scientists						
Education sector						
Research and development sector						
Financial investment institutions						
Research funding agencies						
Policy makers (international level)						
Policy makers (national level)						
Policy makers (regional level)						
Industry regulators (wastewater quality, noise, sludge quality)						
Health and safety inspectors & Controlling institutions						
Government officials						
National Sectoral networks						
Regional Sectoral networks						
International Sectoral networks						
Middleman (who,)						
Other.....						

II PART. Respondent information

Q3 Your organisation activity

- trade production services education research consultation
 NGOs industry other (please fill in)

Q4 The size of your organisation

- < 10 employees 10-49 employees 50-100 employees
 101-200 employees > 201 employees

Q5 Age

- 18-24 25-34 35-49 50-64 65-74 >75

Q6 Gender

- Woman Man Other Prefer not to say

Q7 Education

- Elementary/Middle school High school Vocational school University degree

Q8 Your position held

- manual worker office worker expert/researcher engineer manager
 director / president

Q9 Experience in water/ wastewater sector (years)

- 0-1 2-5 6-10 11-20 21-30 >30